

1 Effect of sanitizing E-beam treatment on the binding capacity of plasma powder used to 2 manufacture restructured dry-cured ham models

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11

12 **Abstract**

13 The manufacture of restructured dry-cured hams involves a contamination risk with pathogens
14 such as *Listeria monocytogenes*. This work studied the effect of E-beam, as sanitizing treatment,
15 on the binding capacity of plasma powder (PP). For that, model systems of restructured boneless
16 dry-cured hams were manufactured by adapting the conventional processing of dry-cured hams
17 to their reduced size. They were contaminated with *L. innocua* as a surrogate and treated
18 bilaterally with 2 kGy. The PP binding properties were determined using tensile tests. The
19 microstructure of the binding area was studied by scanning electron microscopy. The results
20 showed that the binding force increased progressively with the processing time and was not
21 modified by the irradiation treatment. Scanning electron microscopy of the binding area showed
22 increasingly compact and dense structures probably related to changes in proteins structure
23 induced by the treatment.

24

25 **Keywords:** E-beam, restructured dry-cured ham, plasma powder, binding force, microstructure,
26 *Listeria*.

27

28 **1. Introduction**

29 Dry-cured ham is a product made from the whole hind leg of the pig, and the manufacturing
30 process involves a salting process that yields very complex changes that cause not only
31 dehydration of the product but also the development of sensory characteristics. During salting,
32 sufficient salt is provided to produce a gradual dehydration and inhibit spoilage microorganisms.
33 In the post-salting period, salt diffuses into the muscles and the water migrates from the inner
34 meat tissues to the surface. In the drying period, water evaporates due to the steam pressure
35 gradient between the surface of the meat and the air in the drying chamber (Estévez, Ventanas,

36 Morcuende, & Ventanas, 2015; Toldrá & Aristoy, 2010). The loss of water favours a continuous
37 decrease in the weight of the product, and the a_w reaches values close to 0.90, sufficient to inhibit
38 the growth of a large number of microorganisms (ICMSF, 2002; Montville & Matthews, 2013).
39 In the ripening period, the temperature increases to a value favouring the proteolysis and lipolysis
40 reactions, producing volatile compounds directly involved in the flavour development. The
41 whole process can take up to 11-15 months (Mora et al., 2009; Petrova, Aasen, Rustad, &
42 Eikevik, 2015; Toldrá & Aristoy, 2010).

43 Traditionally, dry-cured hams are commercialized in whole pieces (bone-in forms). Nevertheless,
44 the pronounced transformation of dietary habits in the last years has led to the marketing of boned
45 dry-cured ham in different formats, i.e., smaller pieces or slices, that open up a new market for
46 those countries where bone-in presentation is not common or where they are preferred.

47 Ham boning is usually done in the final product, but this process makes it more expensive, not
48 only due to the loss of the lean part that remains attached to the bone but also due to the costs
49 associated with the staff needed to carry it out. The boning of fresh pork legs provides an
50 alternative to avoid these inconveniences, as well as to facilitate handling during ripening.

51 However, the boning involves a loss of the ham shape and changes the external appearance after
52 ripening, which would negatively impact their marketing. As a result, the use of different cold-
53 binding systems for restructuring fresh pork legs has been proposed, thus improving the desirable
54 external appearance. In this way, different binding agents have been successfully assayed, mainly
55 based on proteins such as microbial transglutaminase (Kieliszek & Misiewicz, 2014; Romero de
56 Ávila, Ordóñez, de la Hoz, Herrero, & Cambero, 2010) and various plasma-derived products
57 such as thrombin fibrinogen system, hydrolysates and plasma powder (Flores, Boyle, & Kastner,
58 2007; Ofori & Hsieh, 2016; Romero de Ávila, Ordóñez, Escudero, & Cambero, 2014). The
59 agents develop sufficient interactions with the meat to eliminate the remaining voids that result
60 from the boning process and substantially improve the handling and consistency of the ham.

61 One of the most effective agents is plasma powder (PP), which contains a complex mixture of
62 proteins, such as serum albumin and globulin, and is enriched with fibrinogen. PP is a dehydrated
63 powder product that keeps the functionality of the proteins including gelling and binding
64 capacities. In addition, it does not produce changes in the colour and flavour of the meat products
65 (EFSA, 2015; Toldrá, Lynch, Couture, & Álvarez, 2019).

66 The regulation of the application and labelling of plasma proteins and blood derivatives varies
67 among the different countries. The USA governmental regulation (USDA/FSIS, 2005) permits
68 the use of a mixture of beef fibrinogen and plasma thrombin protein to bind meat pieces at a
69 maximum concentration of 10%. In contrast, the European Union permits its use as a food
70 additive in restructured products but attempts to control it due to possible fraud in which these

71 products could be offered as whole ones. However, no potential fraudulent use of another blood-
72 derived binding agent produced for the same purpose has been described (Ofori & Hsieh, 2016).
73 The boning and restructuring process involve handling that increases the risk of cross-
74 contamination with potentially pathogenic microbiota from the industrial environment,
75 equipment, handlers, etc., including *Listeria monocytogenes* (Morganti et al., 2016; Zuber et al.,
76 2019).

77 This bacterium is one of the major food industry problems because of its morphological,
78 physiological and epidemiological features and the high severity of the human infection named
79 listeriosis. The genetic disposition of *L. monocytogenes* allows it to adapt and survive in adverse
80 environments, developing important mechanisms such as biofilm formation, *quorum sensing* and
81 antimicrobial resistance (Gandhi & Chikindas, 2007).

82 It is possible to find *L. monocytogenes* in dry-cured ham, even in low amounts, as reported by
83 several authors (Cabedo, Picart i Barrot, & Teixido i Canelles, 2008; Giovannini et al., 2007;
84 Gómez et al., 2015; Prencipe et al., 2012). However, the a_w and salt content are two hurdles of
85 *Listeria* growth; the surviving injured cells would lose part of their metabolic capacities, but they
86 can remain as latent cells and recover their capacities when the conditions are favourable. In
87 addition, *Listeria* adapted to survive in hostile environments may have a greater pathogenicity
88 due to the activation of its virulence factors (Gandhi & Chikindas, 2007; Rantsiou, Mataragas,
89 Alessandria, & Cocolin, 2012; Lucas, Alía, Velasco, Selgas, & Cabeza, 2021). The risk of
90 contamination of dry-cured ham with *Listeria* spp. requires the use of sanitizing technologies,
91 such as E-beam whose effectiveness has been demonstrated in both sliced and boned dry-cured
92 hams (Hoz, Cambero, Cabeza, Herrero, & Ordóñez, 2008; Lucas, Selgas, García, Velasco, &
93 Cabeza, 2020; Lucas et al., 2021).

94 However, the efficacy of E-beam to control *Listeria* in restructured hams has not been studied.
95 In this meat product it is also necessary to study the effect of the E-beam on different aspects of
96 the restructuring process, such as the ability of the accelerated electrons to penetrate through the
97 binding area and if they affect the stability and the interaction of the binding agent proteins. If
98 so, it would have an adverse impact on the structure of restructured hams and therefore their
99 marketing. Consequently, the aim of this work is to determine the effect of E-beam on the binding
100 capacity of the plasma powder as a cold binding agent in restructured hams and, consequently, if
101 this non-thermal technology can be also used to sanitize this type of meat product.

102

103 **2. Material and Methods**

104 The model systems of restructured dry-cured hams were prepared using pork meat pieces and
105 plasma powder as the cold-set binding agent. They were processed according to the scheme in
106 Fig. 1.

107 A total of 32 models of restructured meat pieces (RMPs) were manufactured and separated in
108 two clusters of 16 RMP. One cluster (16 RMPs) was contaminated with *L. innocua* (LC) (see
109 Section 2.2) and was used for microbiological analysis. The other cluster (16 RMPs) was non-
110 contaminated (NC) and was used for the study of the physico-chemical parameters, binding
111 properties and microstructure. All the models were manufactured adding plasma powder and then
112 subjected to the binding period and the conditions of the salting and post-salting periods. Later,
113 half of the models of each cluster (8 RMPs) were treated with E-beam (LC-T and NC-T) (see
114 Section 2.3), and the other half (the remainder 8 RMPs) were not treated and were used as the
115 control (LC-NT and NC-NT). Finally, all the models were subjected to the drying/ripening
116 period.

117

118 **2.1. Manufacture of Restructured Meat Pieces models (RMPs).**

119 The RMPs were prepared from boned whole fresh pork legs purchased from a local meat
120 processor located in Madrid (Spain). The external flaps and the distal meat portions were
121 removed to obtain homogeneous pieces. The restructuring of the meat pieces is shown in Fig. 2.
122 They were cut into five blocks of 1 kg in weight, approximately (Fig. 2A). Then, they were cut
123 in half horizontally and opened “like a book” (Fig. 2B). Approximately 20 g of Porcine Plasma
124 Powder FG (Sonac B.V., Loenen, Netherlands) was sprinkled over the two surfaces to cover
125 them in full and allow the two surfaces to touch (Fig. 2C). To favour the binding, the pieces were
126 vacuum packed (20 kPa) in low permeability polyethylene plastic bags (35 cm³/ 24 h m² bars for
127 O₂, 150 cm³/ 24 h m² bars for CO₂) and kept at 4°C for 24 h (binding period) (Fig. 2E). After this
128 time, the RMPs were removed from the plastic bags.

129 The RMPs prepared were submitted to salting and post-salting periods (Fig. 2F). To establish
130 equivalence between the processing of RMPs and conventional dry-cured hams, the length of
131 these phases was adapted to the weight of the model pieces. First, the RMPs were covered with
132 a mixture of coarse and fine salt (1/1) (w/w) and kept at 4°C, 90% RH for 18 h per kg of piece
133 (salting period). After this time, the visible salt was removed from the surface with a brush, and
134 the RMPs were maintained for 3 days at 4°C and 80-90% RH in order to favour the distribution
135 of salt into the inner part (post-salting period). Then, the RMPs were separated into two clusters,
136 and one was submitted to E-beam treatment and the other was not treated (Fig. 1).

137 After treatment, all the RMPs were placed into a chamber at 15°C and 80% RH until the end of
138 the processing, and this period lasted for 33 days approximately (drying/ripening period).

139 The process was controlled by determining a_w and moisture at different times of processing: after
140 binding, salting and post-salting, and at the middle and the end of the drying/ripening period.

141

142 **2.2. Contamination of Restructured Meat Pieces models with *Listeria***

143 A strain of *Listeria innocua* (NCTC 11288) was used as a *L. monocytogenes* surrogate. This
144 strain is more radioresistant than the *L. monocytogenes* strains of major concern in the meat
145 industry (Cabeza, Cambero, de la Hoz, & Ordóñez, 2007; García-Márquez, Ordóñez, Cambero,
146 & Cabeza, 2012; Hoz et al., 2008). In addition, this procedure avoids the risk associated with the
147 handling of pathogenic bacterium.

148 Fresh cultures were prepared for each experiment by inoculating a piece of frozen culture into 9
149 ml of TSB medium and incubating at 32 °C for 24 h. The bacterial load yielded was 10^8 cells/ml,
150 approximately.

151 To contaminate the RMPs, lean pork meat slices (10 g) were prepared using an electric slicer
152 (Slicers ES 300, Beckers Italy) whose rotating blade and contact surfaces were previously deeply
153 cleaned and rinsed with sterile distilled water. 0.5 µl of a *L. innocua* culture (37°C, 24 h) carrying
154 approximately 10^5 cells was deposited in the centre of each slice. The slices were folded and tied
155 with a long twine, and this small package was placed on the surface of the lower half of the meat
156 block previously sprinkled with the PP (Fig. 2D) as described above. The ends of the twine were
157 left outside of the RMPs to easily locate the contaminated slice. The meat blocks were processed
158 as described in Section 2.1.

159

160 **2.3. E-beam treatment**

161 The treatment was performed at the end of the post-salting period. The pieces were transferred
162 in insulated polystyrene boxes at 4°C to the IONISOS Iberica irradiation facility (Cuenca, Spain)
163 which is equipped with an electron accelerator operating at 10 MeV. The dose absorbed by the
164 samples was monitored considering the absorbance of simultaneously treated cellulose triacetate
165 dosimeters (ASTM, 2013) placed on the surface of the RMPs.

166 Doses of 2 kGy were applied bilaterally (on both sides of the product). In previous works
167 performed by our research group (Lucas et al., 2020), it has been observed that this treatment is
168 effective; i.e., the inner part of the piece received a sufficient dose of irradiation to destroy
169 *Listeria*, guaranteeing the microbiological criterion of "zero tolerance" while maintaining the
170 sensory properties of the product.

171

172 **2.4. Physico-chemical parameters**

173 The pH was determined, after homogenization of the sample in distilled water (1:10) (w/v), with
174 a Crison Digit-501 pH-meter (Crison Instruments Ltd., Spain).

175 The a_w value was analysed using a Dew Point Water Activity Meter (AQUALAB 4T, Decagon
176 Devices Inc., WA, USA).

177 The dry matter and the ashes were determined according to the AOAC (2011). The salt content
178 was estimated as the difference between the ash content of fresh and salted RMPs (Romero de
179 Ávila et al., 2010). All analyses were performed in quintuplicate.

180

181 **2.5. Microbial analyses**

182 To count the surviving microorganisms, contaminated slices were located in the RMPs and
183 removed with the help of a sterile scalpel. Five mm around the slice were also removed to ensure
184 its total extraction. The sample was homogenized with 40 ml of sterile saline solution in a
185 Stomacher (Mix2, AES Laboratoire, France). *L. innocua* counts were determined by the pour-
186 plate method using Palcam agar base (Oxoid, Basingstoke, UK) with egg yolk emulsion (Oxoid,
187 Basingstoke, UK) and selective supplement (polymyxin B, acriflavine HCl and ceftazidime,
188 Oxoid, Basingstoke, UK). The plates were incubated at 37°C for 48 h and the colonies were
189 enumerated with a Digital S Colony counter (J. P. Selecta, Barcelona, Spain). Counts were
190 performed in duplicate and the results were expressed in log CFU.

191

192 **2.6. Plasma Powder (PP) binding force**

193 To determinate the binding force of PP, a uniaxial tensile test was performed according to
194 Romero de Ávila et al. (2014), using a TA.XT2i Stable Micro System Texture Analyser (Stable
195 Microsystems Ltd., England). A 5 kg load cell was employed. Samples of approximately 0.4 cm
196 high x 2 cm wide x 2 cm long were taken from the binding line of each RMP (both treated and
197 non-treated) using a scalpel, ensuring that the binding line was always in the centre of the sample.
198 The analysis was carried out with an A/MTG probe consisting of two tensile grips placed at a
199 distance of 15 mm from each other. One tensile grip was fixed onto the base of the textural
200 analyser, while the other one was attached to the load cell. The samples were clamped between
201 the two grips and a constant traction of 0.5 mm/s was applied until rupture. The rupture force
202 was determined as the maximum force peak height (N) required for breaking the sample and the
203 binding force was calculated from the rupture force according to the Eq. 1.

204

$$205 \text{ Binding force (N.cm}^{-2}\text{)} = \frac{\text{Rupture force (N)}}{\text{Cross sectional area of the sample}} \quad (1)$$

206
207
208

209 Where the Cross-sectional area of the sample is equal to the thickness of the sample (cm)
210 multiplied by its width (cm).

211

212 **2.7. Microstructure determination**

213 The microstructure of the binding area of RMPs was determined by scanning electron
214 microscopy (SEM) at the Microscopy and Cytometry Center of Complutense University. Several
215 cubes (approximately 0.5 cm for each side) were cut in the binding area using a scalpel, ensuring
216 that the binding line was always in the centre of the cube. The samples were fixed for 5 h at 4°C
217 in buffer milling (2.5% glutaraldehyde and 4% paraformaldehyde), and then, they were
218 dehydrated by immersion in gradually increasing concentrations of acetone solutions, from 30 to
219 100%, and maintained twice for fifteen minutes in each concentration. Finally, the samples were
220 dried in liquid critical point carbon dioxide and sputter-coated with gold and graphite. The
221 samples were kept in a desiccator until the time of visualization. Micrographs of each sample
222 were taken by the SEM at 20 kV (JEOL, mod. JSM-6400, Japan) at different magnifications
223 (x100, x1000 and x5000). A minimum of five representative pictures at each magnification were
224 taken using an Inca Oxford image capture system (Oxford Instruments Analytical Ltd., High
225 Wycombe, UK) and the most representative ones were selected.

226

227 **2.8. Statistical analysis**

228 Data were analysed using IBM SPSS Statistics v23.0 software for Windows (SPSS Inc., Chicago,
229 IL, USA). To assess differences in the physico-chemical parameters and binding force between
230 irradiated and untreated samples, one-way ANOVA was conducted. *P* values of less than 0.05
231 were regarded as statistically significant.

232

233 **3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

234

235 **3.1. Physico-chemical parameters**

236 At first, the conditions of the conventional processing (time, humidity and temperature) of dry-
237 cured ham were adapted to obtain RMPs with similar characteristics to those of dry cured ham
238 and therefore to establish if the model is useful for the purpose of this work.

239 Fig. 3 shows a comparison between the changes of moisture and the a_w during the processing of
240 both RMPs and conventional dry-cured hams. The values of the conventional ones were taken
241 from the data reported by other authors (Asensio & Díaz, 2001; Ventanas & Cava, 2001). In
242 general terms, these physico-chemical parameters evolve in a similar way in both meat products,
243 although they vary slightly.

244 In the conventional dry-cured hams, the moisture described by the mentioned authors goes from
245 initial values close to 70% (corresponding to fresh pork leg) to 65% in the post-salting period
246 and to 55% at the end of the drying period. In the RMPs, the moisture values determined in these
247 periods were very similar: $75.0 \pm 0.9\%$, $67.4 \pm 2.4\%$ and $58.2 \pm 1.8\%$, respectively.

248 The a_w decreased from initial values of 0.990 to 0.968 in the post-salting period in both products
249 to 0.894 and 0.880 at the end of the drying period in RPMs and conventional dry-cured hams,
250 respectively.

251 The pH value of the RMPs remained close to 6.0 throughout the process. However, several
252 authors reported a possible pH increase up to 6.5 at the end of the drying period in conventional
253 products. This has been described as a consequence of the proteolysis occurring in this period
254 and the subsequent formation of non-protein nitrogen (Losantos, Sanabria, Cornejo, &
255 Carrascosa, 2000; Mora et al., 2009; Petrova et al., 2015; Sánchez-Molinero & Arnau, 2008). In
256 this study, this increase was not observed in the RPMs probably due to that the time required for
257 ripening was much shorter than in conventional dry-cured hams and minor proteolysis occurred.

258 After the binding period, the ash content was 2.63 ± 0.79 g/100 g dry matter (DM) and after the
259 drying period, it was 7.01 ± 0.51 g/100 g DM. It is a consequence of the salt migration into the
260 muscles and the loss of water. The salt content determined at the same periods was 1.31 ± 0.79
261 and 5.71 ± 0.51 g/100 g DM, respectively. These results are similar to those previously reported
262 by several authors in conventional dry-cured hams (Bosse et al., 2018; Petrova et al., 2015).

263 The similarity of the behaviour of physico-chemical parameters in both products allows
264 establishing that the adaptation of the traditional manufacture process proposed is adequate and
265 that the RMPs could be considered as a model of dry-cured ham useful for the investigations
266 carried out in this work.

267 When the samples were irradiated at doses of 2 kGy, no significant changes in the physico-
268 chemical parameters were observed. These results are consistent with those described by other
269 authors regarding these same parameters in other E-beam treated foods such as smoked salmon
270 (Medina et al., 2009), cheese (Velasco, Ordóñez, Cabeza, de la Hoz, & Cambero, 2011; Velasco,
271 Ordóñez, Cambero, & Cabeza, 2015) and pork loin, both fresh and marinated (García-Márquez,
272 Cambero, Ordóñez, & Cabeza, 2012; García-Márquez, Ordóñez, et al., 2012). These authors did
273 not detect significant differences between the values of non-irradiated products and those
274 irradiated at doses below 10 kGy.

275

276 **3.2. Effect of E-beam treatment on binding force of the plasma powder**

277 The binding zone appeared as a very faint white line scarcely visible in a simple view. The union
278 line of the RMPs remained always stable and firm during the entire processing time and the

279 RMPs gave the appearance of a single piece, both in the irradiated and non-irradiated samples.
280 Fig. 4 represents the binding force of the PP obtained by a uniaxial tensile test performed in non-
281 irradiated RMPs at different processing periods: binding, salting, post-salting and in the middle
282 (19 days) and at the end of drying (38 days). The results showed a progressive increase within
283 the processing time, from $0.78 \pm 0.15 \text{ N.cm}^{-2}$ after binding to $1.96 \pm 0.52 \text{ N.cm}^{-2}$ at the end of
284 the drying period, but a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) was only observed between the binding
285 force determined in the initial stages (binding and salting) and at the end of the drying period. It
286 could be related to changes in the structures of proteins as a result of decreased moisture and
287 increased salt content, which favour the increase of covalent cross-links among proteins and
288 consequently, the interactions between PP and meat proteins (Kramer, Shende, Motl, Pace, &
289 Scholtz, 2012). In addition, these authors also indicated that the water content reduction promotes
290 a decrease in the solubility of proteins. The results agree with those obtained by Romero de Ávila
291 et al. (2014) in restructured dry-cured ham.

292 When the tensile tests were performed in irradiated RMPs, no significant differences ($p > 0.05$)
293 were observed vs. the non-irradiated ones (Fig. 5), which indicate that the E-beam treatment did
294 not affect the binding capacity of the PP.

295 These results are interesting from an industrial point of view because if the strength at which the
296 RMPs remain together is stable, it makes them easy to handle even when they are subjected to
297 size reduction operations, such as slicing, the preparation of blocks or their transformation into
298 RTE products, facilitating their marketing.

299

300 **3.3. Microstructure determination by SEM**

301 Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 correspond to images obtained by SEM with a magnification of x 5000. In Fig.
302 6, the microstructure of the binding line of untreated RMPs after the post-salting period can be
303 observed. The line appears like a disorganized network of crisscrossed fibrous structures. This
304 structure may correspond to cross-links that arise between the proteins when, as mentioned
305 above, they lose their structure as a consequence of the salt content.

306 Fig. 7 presents two images obtained from the binding line at the end of the drying period in
307 untreated (A) and treated (B) samples. In this case, it can be observed that this structure changes
308 and looks more organized and firmer, and the proteins of the binding line (plasma) appear as
309 thicker and retracted filaments that interconnect with the meat surface (Fig. 7A). The image could
310 correspond to a possible retraction occurring when the proteins are dehydrated as a consequence
311 of the loss of water during the drying period. These results agree with the increase of binding
312 force obtained from results of the tensile test (Section 3.2). Romero de Ávila et al. (2014) also

313 reported the establishments of links between PP and meat proteins during the salting period and
314 indicated that they were stable and became compact structures during dehydration.

315 When the E-beam treatment (2 kGy) was applied to the RPMs, the image of the binding area
316 changes drastically (Fig. 7B). An unstructured, more compact and denser mass was observed and
317 almost no fibrous structures were present. This image could be the representation of the intense
318 conformational changes occurring in the proteins of the binding agent or the meat proteins as a
319 result of the irradiation treatment. Indeed, Lee, Lee, & Song (2003) and Chmielewski, Haji-Saeid,
320 & Ahmed (2005) indicated that irradiation produces free radicals that promote the formation of
321 new and numerous cross-links among proteins, resulting in an intense modification of their
322 structure. Yoon (2003) also observed changes in the microstructure of gamma-irradiated (2.9
323 kGy) meat proteins from chicken breast and reported a myofibrillary shrinkage (decrease in
324 sarcoma width) associated with a significantly firmer texture. Other authors observed changes in
325 a wide variety of proteins from different sources (whey, soya, fish, prawn, gluten and collagen,
326 among others) with high irradiation doses (>10 kGy) (Benbettaieb, Karbowski, Brachais, &
327 Debeaufort, 2016; Inamura et al., 2013; Jo, Kang, Lee, Kwon, & Byun, 2005; Lacroix et al.,
328 2002; Lee, Lee, & Song, 2005; Mahto, Ghosh, Das, & Das, 2015; Ouattara, Canh, Vachon,
329 Mateescu, & Lacroix, 2002; Sabato, Nakamurakare, & Sobral, 2007). Zhao et al. (2017) also
330 observed a more compact structure in walnut flour proteins when E-beam treatment was applied
331 at a dose of 2.5 kGy.

332 The effect of irradiation is directly related to the water content of the food. Tahergorabi,
333 Jaczynski, & Matak (2014) reported that in food matrix with low water content, the proteins are
334 minimally affected by radiation because of the scarce production of hydroxyl or superoxide anion
335 radicals generated by the radiolysis of water. Moreover, Lee et al. (2003) described the effect of
336 gamma-irradiation at different doses (1-10 kGy) on plasma proteins and observed two types of
337 patterns. In powdered proteins, irradiation did not influence the functional properties of proteins
338 (solubility, viscosity) and there was not a significant change in terms of molecular weight profile.
339 However, when the proteins were in solution (hydrated), significant changes were detected, even
340 at doses as low as 1 kGy. At this dose, the radicals generated by the water radiolysis caused the
341 protein to fragment into low molecular weight polypeptide chains. However, by gradually
342 increasing the irradiation dose (2-10 kGy), various types of interactions between proteins are
343 established, resulting in high molecular weight aggregates.

344 In our case, it is possible that the water present on the meat surface during post-salting could
345 cause some degree of hydration of PP. Subsequently, E-beam treatment would favour the
346 formation of free radicals and the aggregation of proteins, resulting in the observation of
347 ultrastructural changes (Fig. 7B) and the increase of binding forces determined in the tensile test.

349 **3.4. Listericide effect of E-beam treatment in RMPs**

350 In the untreated RMPs, the *L. innocua* counts decreased 0.5 log CFU during the first 3 days of
351 processing, coinciding with the salting period. Then, the counts increased to initial levels (10^5
352 CFU) at the end of the post-salting period (4th day of processing). This behaviour seems to be
353 related to the conditions created in the RMPs during the early stages and mainly to the increase
354 of the salt concentration. The salt leads to a slight *Listeria* destruction until they adapt to the new
355 environment and recover to the initial levels, remaining constant throughout the remainder of the
356 processing time (Fig. 8).

357 Several authors also indicated that dry-cured hams do not support the growth of *L.*
358 *monocytogenes* due to their low water activity (<0.92) (European Commission, 2007; ICMSF,
359 2002), and therefore, they have a very long shelf life. Nevertheless, the effectiveness of a low a_w
360 (0.908) value was described in reducing the pathogenic populations of *L. monocytogenes*,
361 *Salmonella* spp. and *E. coli* O157:H7 down to undetectable levels under dry-cured ham
362 elaboration conditions (Montiel et al., 2020; Reynolds, Harrison, Rose-Morrow, & Lyon, 2001;
363 Serra-Castelló, Jofré, Garriga, & Bover-Cid, 2020). Other factors, such as pH and nitrite content,
364 enhance the stability of the products by acting synergistically (Asensio & Díaz, 2001;
365 Portocarrero, Newman, & Mikel, 2002; Stollewerk, Jofré, Comaposada, Arnau, & Garriga,
366 2014). Sadeghi-Mehr, Lautenschlaeger, & Drusch (2016) reported that the combination of
367 intrinsic (pH and a_w) and extrinsic (fermentation and drying conditions) factors during the
368 processing of restructured dry-cured hams could reduce the load of *L. monocytogenes* and
369 *Salmonella* spp. up to 1.25 and 2.28 log CFU/g, respectively.

370 However, the results of this work show that *Listeria* remains latent and adapts to adverse
371 conditions which agree with the results obtained by other authors in different dry-cured products.
372 Prencipe et al. (2012) reported that *L. monocytogenes* is not completely eliminated during the
373 processing of Parma ham. Morales-Partera et al. (2017) observed a similar behaviour in cured
374 pork loin, obtaining 0.8 decimal reductions in the initial processing stage.

375 When the RMPs were submitted to a bilateral treatment of 2 kGy, the load of *Listeria* decreased
376 at least 5 log units, to undetectable levels. For *L. monocytogenes* load, the Commission
377 Regulation (EC 1441/2007) sets a maximum of 10^2 CFU/g during the shelf-life for foods
378 different than those intended for sensitive populations. Consequently, the results obtained in this
379 work show that the treatment applied is suitable to eliminate this pathogen completely.

380 In addition, these results are in total agreement with the results of numerous authors (Cabeza et
381 al., 2007; Cabeza et al., 2010; Cabeza, de la Hoz, Velasco, Cambero, & Ordóñez, 2009; García-
382 Márquez, Ordóñez, et al., 2012; Hoz et al., 2008; Lucas et al., 2020; Lucas et al., 2021; Medina

383 et al., 2009; Song et al., 2009; Velasco et al., 2015) who performed similar studies on different
384 foods such as RTE meat products, cheese or several fishes such as salmon and smoked tuna.
385 They reported that doses of 1-2.5 kGy guarantee the microbiological safety of the different foods,
386 increasing their shelf life, and that these treatments are sufficient to achieve the FSO for *Listeria*
387 *monocytogenes* according to the EU and USDA statements (Neri et al., 2019).

388

389 **4. Conclusion**

390 The model systems of restructured dry-cured hams developed in this work are adequate for
391 studying the changes occurring during the processing of dry-cured hams. Doses of 2 kGy applied
392 bilaterally in these restructured products are useful for sanitation purposes. The microstructure
393 of the binding area revealed protein structural modifications of the irradiated restructured meat
394 pieces since a denser and more compact matrix was observed. However, non-significant changes
395 were observed in the binding force of the plasma powder used as a cold-binding agent due to the
396 E-beam treatment. The post-irradiation stability of this restructuring methodology is attractive
397 for possible industrial/commercial use.

398

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404

405 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

406 None

407

408 **Author contribution statement**

409 The authors contributed equally to this manuscript

410

411 **References**

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622 **Figures**

623

624 **Fig. 1.** Schematic representation of the phases of the study.

625 LC: *Listeria* contaminated; NC: Noncontaminated

626 LC-NT: *Listeria* contaminated-nontreated; LC-T: *Listeria* contaminated-treated

627 NC-NT: Noncontaminated-nontreated; NC-T: Noncontaminated-treated

628

629 **Fig. 2.** Manufacturing process of the restructured meat pieces: A. Original meat pieces
630 (approximately 1 kg); B. Horizontal cutting of the meat piece (open "like a book"); C. Plasma
631 powder sprinkled on the cutting surfaces; D. Placing the slice of meat contaminated with *Listeria*
632 (enclosed in the dashed circle) on the cutting surface sprinkled with plasma powder; E.
633 Reassembling the meat piece and vacuum packaging for the binding period; F. View of the
634 restructured meat piece after undergoing the salting phase.

635

636 **Fig. 3.** Evolution of moisture (grey lines) and water activity (black lines) during processing of
637 restructured meat pieces (continued lines) and conventional dry-cured ham (discontinued lines).

638

639 **Fig. 4.** Binding force ($\text{N}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$) of untreated restructured meat pieces at different times of
640 processing: B (binding period), S (salting period), PS (post-salting period), HDR (half of the
641 drying/ripening period) and EDR (at the end of the drying/ripening period).

642

643 **Fig. 5.** Binding force ($\text{N}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$) of protein plasma powder in irradiated (2 kGy) (grey) and non-
644 irradiated (white) restructured meat pieces at the half of the drying/ripening period (HDR) and at
645 the end of the drying/ripening period (EDR).

646

647 **Fig. 6.** Scanning electron microscopy micrographs of the binding line from non-treated
648 restructured meat pieces after the post-salting period (magnification x 5000).

649

650 **Fig. 7.** Scanning electron microscopy micrographs of the binding line of restructured meat pieces
651 at the end of the drying/ripening period (magnification x 5000): (A) non-treated; (B) treated.

652

653 **Fig. 8.** Counts of *Listeria innocua* (log CFU) in non-irradiated restructured meat pieces on
654 different days of processing.

Figure 6

10µm

CRedit author statement

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AUTHOR DECLARATION

We wish to confirm that there are no known conflicts of interest associated with the publication “Effect of sanitizing E-beam treatment on the binding capacity of plasma powder used to manufacture restructured dry-cured ham models” and there has been no significant financial support for this work that could have influenced its outcome.

We confirm that the manuscript has been read and approved by all named authors and that there are no other persons who satisfied the criteria for authorship but are not listed. We further confirm that the order of authors listed in the manuscript has been approved by all of us. We also confirm that we have given due consideration to the protection of intellectual property associated with this work and that there are no impediments to publication, including the timing of publication, with respect to intellectual property. In so doing we confirm that we have followed the regulations of our institutions concerning intellectual property.

We understand that the Corresponding Author is the sole contact for the Editorial process (including Editorial Manager and direct communications with the office). Juan Raúl Lucas López is responsible for communicating with the other authors about progress, submissions of revisions and final approval of proofs. We confirm that we have provided a current, correct email address which is accessible by the Corresponding Author and which has been configured to accept email from jrlucas.pe@gmail.com

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